

IMPROVEMENT OF SALES CHANNELS IN SMALL AND PRIVATE ENTERPRISES

Jurakulov Odiljon Mamatolib ugli

student of Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service
60412500-Marketing (by branches and spheres)

Abstract: the article describes the three-stage interrelated activities based on marketing principles in the formation of sales channels in small and private enterprises. Work, activities and their improvement on the basis of marketing and logistics principles were considered at each stage.

Key words: sales channels, warehousing, long-term storage, attractive sales channel, transportation, level of market fragmentation, vertical sales channel.

INTRODUCTION. The formation of sales channels begins with the creation of a systematic process that can positively affect the activity of small and private enterprises in the delivery of goods to the final consumer. The activity of the sales channel is systematic, and the operations performed in it are carried out sequentially. It is impossible to switch to another without completing one transaction in the sales channel. The type of operations performed in the sales process is related to the activities of small and private enterprises. There is no universal sales channel for all small and private enterprises. Each small and private enterprise independently forms its own sales channels. Through the sales channel, small business entities should be able to sell their goods at the right place and at the right time.

Formation of sales channels is based on marketing principles. Because all sales operations are directed to the consumer. A sales channel is placed depending on the location of the consumer, the potential sales volume of the sales channel is

determined based on the consumer's purchase cycle, the retail prices of goods are determined based on the behavior of the stores, the volume of services of sales staff, and the level of income of consumers. Therefore, the central place in the formation of sales channels is occupied by the consumer. In addition, many options for making decisions from marketing principles are also applicable in this process. There are several methods of the sales channel, the choice of which one is based on the entrepreneur's decision as the most optimal option.

MAIN PART. The final result of the entrepreneur's activity becomes clear after the sale of the produced product. The maximum profit of the entrepreneur depends on the sales activity. The main task of an entrepreneur is to organize an optimal sales network for the effective sale of manufactured products. In order to organize sales activities, an entrepreneur must first form sales channels. Building sales channels involves three interrelated steps based on marketing principles:

I. Preparatory stage. At this stage, the entrepreneur should study the factors that can affect the delivery of products to the place of sale. Delivery and sale of products to the place of sale is the responsibility of the sales channels formed by the entrepreneur. Therefore, at this stage, the entrepreneur should choose the form of the sales channel that is most suitable for him. For this, the following factors should be taken into account:

a) Product features, i.e. functional features, packaging, shelf life, seasonality of production and demand, etc. An entrepreneur should be well aware of the circumstances in which the characteristics of his manufactured product may be violated. This allows for the proper organization of storage conditions so that the chemical composition of the product does not deteriorate, packaging to prevent damage to the external environment and damage during transport, and product transportation to avoid delaying the delivery in accordance with the constant needs of the products.

Therefore, it is appropriate for an entrepreneur to choose one or another type

of sale based on the characteristics of the product. In order to sell products that require warehousing and long-term storage directly through the channel, an entrepreneur must first have a special warehouse, and secondly, storage, placement, unloading, loading and transportation costs arise. If the entrepreneur sells products of this type through an indirect channel, the operations and costs related to warehousing, storage and preparation for sale will be borne by intermediaries.

The characteristics of certain types of products that should be taken into account in the formation of sales channels are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Product characteristics affecting the formation of sales channels

№	Product type	Indicators	Property	Recommended attractive channel shape
1.	Milk	Functional feature	Perishable;	The fact that the product does not require long-term storage and is perishable, as well as daily consumption, requires distribution through a direct channel. Because during the transfer from hand to hand through an indirect channel, there may be changes in the composition, and the increase in loading and
		packaging	Short-term goods;	
		Warehousing	It is kept hermetically closed in special packaging such as metal, glass, cardboard in various sizes.	
		Transportation	Does not require long-term storage;	
		Consumption		

		cycle (speed, turnover)		unloading during transport may delay the consumption period.
2.	Processed fruit and vegetable preserves	Functional characteristics	Should be delivered in a short period of time;	The fact that the consumption period of the product is seasonal, that it requires special storage, that the product is divided into batches and that the stock of goods is created directly through the channel is a big cost for the entrepreneur. Therefore, it may be attractive for an entrepreneur to use an indirect channel.
		packaging	Transported in packed containers;	
		Warehousing		
		Transportation	A commodity for daily consumption	
		Consumption cycle	Traditional;	
3.	Building materials (wood, board)	Functional feature	A durable product	Storing materials and finding a buyer require high costs for an entrepreneur, so it is advisable to use the services of retailers.
		packaging	Hermetically packed in glass and special containers	
		Warehousing	Can be stored for a long time;	

	Transportation	It should be collected in warehouses and divided into batches of goods.	
	Consumption cycle	Requires loading, transportation, unloading;	

2. Location of the enterprise (relative to the consumer). Before starting any business, any entrepreneur decides where to locate his business. An entrepreneur places his enterprise according to the location of raw materials, consumers and transport communication. The location of the enterprise is also taken into account in the formation of sales channels. Here, the sales channel is formed taking into account the distance between the enterprise and the consumer and the time of product delivery. In relation to the location of the enterprise, as the number and dispersion of geographical points where consumers are located increases, it is more effective to use an indirect channel than a direct channel.

3. Market fragmentation. Entrepreneurs try to place their trade networks around markets that organize consumers. If several markets are close to the location of the enterprise, the entrepreneur tries to cover all markets. But not all entrepreneurs have the opportunity to cover all markets only through a direct channel. In this case, it is appropriate for the entrepreneur to use indirect channel forms.

4. Price (costs). An entrepreneur should take into account the expected costs when forming a sales channel. All operations performed in the sales channel require

a cost. All costs associated with product distribution are added to the cost of the product and determine the selling price of the product. The entrepreneur should calculate how much it will cost until the product reaches the final consumer. If the financial capabilities of the entrepreneur do not reach the costs, it is effective to entrust the further movement of the product to the discretion of intermediaries. Here, the entrepreneur has the opportunity to control the cost of the product, the price of selling the product to intermediaries, and the intermediary's mark-up, and ultimately calculate the profit that the entrepreneur and the intermediary can receive.

5. Sales volume. The main goal of creating sales channels for an entrepreneur is to increase the volume of sales to the maximum level. If the sales channel cannot provide sufficient volume of sales, the stock of goods will exceed the norm. As a result, the extended reproduction process of the entrepreneur will suffer a lot. Therefore, if an entrepreneur compares the volume of product production and the sales opportunities of the channel, it will allow to find answers to the questions of whether the future sales channel will be able to ensure that the entrepreneur's production reserves are in order or not.

II. Formation stage. At this stage, the entrepreneur studies the wholesale and retail trade networks in which he operates. At the stage of formation of sales channels, the entrepreneur mainly deals with processes related to commercial work, that is, preparation and conducting of negotiations on sales contracts, conclusion of contracts, control of their implementation, etc.

An entrepreneur can use four different situations when forming a suitable sales channel for him:

1. Existing and effective - the entrepreneur should develop a penetration program in this situation. There is a sales network suitable for the product the entrepreneur is producing and it is efficient in terms of costs and sales volume. It is necessary to establish cooperation with this sales channel. For this, an entrepreneur

should conduct commercial activities at a high level and develop his own penetration program.

2. Available, but limited - in this situation, it is necessary to evaluate the possibilities of penetration of the entrepreneur. There is a suitable channel for the entrepreneur's activity, but it is occupied by competitors. The entrepreneur should evaluate the possibilities of penetrating this channel. In this, the number of competitors, their sales strategies and tactics, interactions in the sales system are studied, and it is determined whether the possibility of penetration is high or low.

3. Availability is unknown - in this situation, the entrepreneur needs to identify the channel. There is no information about the location of the channel or the start of activity for the entrepreneur. But other competitors are using the channel. An entrepreneur must first determine the channel, and secondly, calculate how effective the channel is.

4. Does not exist - in this situation, the entrepreneur should create a channel. In this situation, the entrepreneur must create the channel from start to finish. This process is the most difficult for an entrepreneur. Because any sales channel needs special sales outlets, special storage points, and showrooms. If the financial situation of the businessman is not good, he cannot take advantage of this situation.

III. Design stage. At this stage, the structure of the selected channel is considered. That is, who participates in the channel, the length of the channel, the distribution of costs in the channel, and ways of managing the channel are studied.

1. Identification of participants. In addition to entrepreneurs and consumers, what types of intermediaries are participating in the channel, their working methods and experience are studied.

2. Determining the length of the channel. The length of the channel is determined based on the number of participants. If the length of the channel increases, the speed of circulation of goods slows down and the price of goods becomes more expensive. The length of the channel should be ensured by the

entrepreneur.

3. Calculation of channel costs. The distribution of the costs incurred in the channel among the participants, how much of the expenses the entrepreneur will cover at his own expense, and ultimately how much the impact of this cost will be on the entrepreneur's benefit is calculated.

4. Determining ways (methods) of channel management. The question of whether the entrepreneur will manage the channel from start to finish or whether the channel participants will act separately should be decided at the stage of channel design.

CONCLUSION. Increasing the competitiveness of operating small business entities in the increasingly competitive environment, achieving economic efficiency and ensuring their successful operation in the market is becoming an urgent issue. The solution to this problem is largely related to the optimization of transaction costs of small business entities. Selection of sales channels and continuous control over their effectiveness is one of the most important decisions of marketing service. When evaluating the effectiveness of sales channels, it is necessary to analyze the amount of financial resources necessary for the development of the channel, the potential volume of sales, the current expenses spent on supporting this channel and obtaining income from it, the possibility of controlling the formation of the final price of the product, and the conditions of cooperation.

The need for a systematic analysis of the product sales network is also justified by the need for sales managers to efficiently allocate their working time. Marketing specialists of small and private enterprises producing food products should work with customers who buy goods to provide them with additional discounts and special offers, or to create conditions for the delivery of the product and preferential payment for the product. In this case, periodic evaluations of this group of customers should be the task of the marketing service in order to prevent

them from causing more difficulties than benefits to the enterprise. The costs of small business entities related to the distribution of goods are formed as part of the total logistics costs. Not all small business entities have the same logistics operations. Therefore, in general, it is difficult to show directions for improving the efficiency of small business entities. In order to find a solution to this problem, we classified small business entities according to logistic criteria and showed ways to increase efficiency for each classification of small business entities.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Resolution No. PQ-292 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 4, 2023 "On measures to implement the tasks set in the open dialogue of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan with entrepreneurs in 2023"
2. Resolution No. PQ-306 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 14, 2023 "On financial and institutional support measures for small business development"
3. Gary Armstrong, Philip Kotler, Michael Harker, Ross Brennan. Marketing an introduction. 13th Edition. England, 2017, Paperback: 675 pages, Pearson.
4. Kholmamatov Diyor Haqberdievich, Boyjigitov Sanjarbek Komiljon ugli. Marketing Problems in the development of Export activities of small business entities.
5. Kholmamatov Diyor Haqberdievich. Develop Criteria for Selecting Distribution Channels in Small Business. Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability, 2022
6. Diyor Kholmamatov Haqberdievich. Modern Methods of Developing Wholesale Trade in Agricultural Products. Commonwealth Journal of Academic Research (CJAR.EU). 2022, 8-14 pp.
7. Kholmamatov Diyor Haqberdievich. Current issues in The Development of Marketing logistics in Wholesale trade. Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability, 2021. 13-19 pp.

8. Kholmammatov Diyor Haqberdievich. Marketing issues related to the development of wholesale trade in B2B in Uzbekistan. Modern scientific challenges and trends, 2020. 25-33 pp.
9. Холмаматов Д.Х. Актуальные вопросы логистического обслуживания в оптовой торговле. Инновации и инвестиции, 2019ю 292-294 с.
10. Холмаматов Д.Х. Роль маркетинговой логистики в развитии покупательского обслуживания в оптовой продаже. Наука сегодня: Опыт, традиции, инновации. Материалы международной научно-практической конференции. Вологда, 2021. 12-13 с.
11. Kholmammatov Diyor Haqberdievich. Marketing research to study the demand for bread and bakery products. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 2022. 87-92 pp.
12. Kholmammatov Diyor Haqberdievich. Analysis of the Business Environment Created in Uzbekistan to Increase the Export Potential of Free Economic Zones. American Journal of Economics and Business Management. 133-140 pp.
13. Дж.Б.Эргашев. Маркетинговые исследования в сфере цифрового маркетинга в деятельности малого бизнеса. Экономика и социум, 2023, 868-876 с.
14. Ergashev J.B. IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN SMALL BUSINESSES. ФОРУМ МОЛОДЫХ УЧЕНЫХ 3(79) 2023, 7-10 pp.
15. <https://www.stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/small-business-and-entrepreneurship-2>